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**GEOLOCATION AND STUDY OF HOUSEHOLD WELL WATER IN RELATION
TO CONTAMINANTS AS HEALTH MAPPING TOOL IN KUMBA, SOUTH
WEST REGION, CAMEROON**

By

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Abstract

The poor level of public water supply gives the water Wells an important place in the life of the population of Kumba. Unfortunately, its quality is a major challenge. With the present population growth rate estimated at about 4% annually, more inhabitants turn to these sources of water. The objective of this study is to geolocate the water wells and their contaminants sources at Anglican Quarter, Kumba I Subdivision, and also to realize the chemical analyses of the water collected. By so doing, helping the sanitation authorities to realize the health map of Anglican and to show the importance of GIS in health. The coordinates of the wells and the contaminants sources were taken with a GPS receiver and their depths through a plumb bulb and a tape. The chemical analyses of sample water collected were done in a laboratory. Tape was used to obtain proximity of wells and the contaminants falling between 0 to 15m and above. The result shows that 3.3% of well have good pH according to WHO, 16,7% in nitrate, and concerning electrical conductivity, no well met the WHO norms when 3,3% in chloride. This result can directly help the health authorities to identify the types of water diseases located in the quarters studied.

Keys words: Contaminants, Wells, WHO norms, Geolocation.

1 Introduction

GIS is defined as Geographic Information Systems. It is a science that helps to represent and analyse phenomena in a spatial pattern. Water is very important both for domestic and agricultural consumption such as animals rearing, crops irrigation, etc.; this explains why the spatial prediction of the water table is very important for urban and environmental management activities (Augusto et al., 2016) through water wells or boreholes. Well water comes from underground aquifers, which are pockets of water with bedrock located at different depths (Skillings and Sons, 2018). The depth of the water table can be used to determine the effects of season, climate, or human impact on groundwater (NGS, 2022; Akter et al., 2013). With the poor level of public water supply system in town, a vast majority of households have turned to groundwater (hand-dug well or borehole) and surface water through streams and springs and this does not always goes without risks. Some well water may sometimes not be good for human usage because of contaminants. Some of them are Giardia, Cryptosporidium, and E.coli, which is a type of Coliform bacteria. These microbes can cause diseases as e-coli provides evidence through recent faecal contamination and detection (Sworobuk et al., 1987; Bahel et al., 2021) for instance. Also, there are other contaminants caused by floods and infiltration in most wells. These infected wells may cause diseases like candida commonly known as vaginal itches, skin rashes and other related skin diseases. Wastewater environment is an ideal medium for both pathogenic and non-pathogenic microorganisms (Abdel-Raouf et al., 2012). But WHO (2006) and EPA (2016) recommended zero values for total coliform and E-coli. Henceforth, the goal of this work is to provide the sanitation and municipal authorities with a decision making tool for the improvement of the population health of studied area by supplying them with public water system. Specifically, this study aims at geolocating water well and the influencing factors sources of their contamination (pit toilets, dust bins and sewage tanks), analysing the physico-chemical parameters of well water in the laboratory, mapping all the well water and their contaminants sources and proposing a spatial analysis of the contamination.

2 Literature Review

The study of well water in Kumba is not new. It has been given keen attention by Akoachere and Ngwesse (2016), where they worked on the saturated hydraulic conductivities and high yield zones. Then, the following year, they worked on the darcy and apparent velocities of groundwater (Akoachere and Ngwesse, 2017a). They also worked on the biological water quality of hand-dug wells (Akoachere and Ngwesse, 2017b). Two years later, Akoachere and Ngwesse (2019) did some work on trace metals in groundwater of Kumba and environs. Well water is predominantly used by the population of Kumba for drinking, cooking, washing and agricultural purpose. But very little has been done on the sources and proximity to contaminants especially with the growing population and increased human activities that greatly impact the quality of water. Sometimes these wells are contaminated willingly by some individuals. According to Law No 96/12 of the 5th of August 1996 Section II article 29 and 36 (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 1996) which states that 'direct and indirect spill incidents,

discharges, dumping of any kind and more generally any act likely to provide surface or underground water degradation through the modification of their physical, chemical, biological or bacteriological characteristics shall be prohibited. This law is punishable in article 82 of the same law. Groundwater moves along a flow path perpendicular to equipotential lines and the direction of movement is from lines of higher value to lines of lower value (Oborie & Nwankwoala, 2017). This explains that contaminants can be picked by flowing water from upstream to downstream or from points of higher elevations to low lying areas. The subsurface flow can be much more complex due to heterogeneity of landscape, soil, and hydrogeological environments (McDonnell et al, 2021; Somers and McKenzie, 2020). The presence of wells in almost every compound in Kumba gives a broader picture of their major contaminants. This work was in the Anglican Quarter of Kumba I Subdivision.

The Study Area

Located in the economic capital of the South West region of Cameroon and headquarter of the Meme Division, Kumba sits on the far shadow of the Mount Cameroon. It lies between longitude E9°27'00" and E09°24'15" and Latitude N4°39'45" and N4°38'00" (Figure 1). Kumba has three Sub-Divisions namely Kumba I, II and III and extends over 286km² with average elevation of 240m above mean sea level. It has an estimated population of about 400,000 with three quarters of this population being youth (NISC, 2021). It has Flat lands around the Buea Road area with few hills at Government Station, Meta Quarters, New Quarters, Hausa Quarters, as well as downhill quarters in Mbonge Road neighbourhoods like Meboka, Makata, Nkamalekum, Kosala, Malende, Malabo and Saker C.B.C Field being flood prone. As such, Kumba is characterized by a kind of undulating relief. It is one of the largest cocoa cash crop producing areas in the country (Akoachere et al., 2019). Kumba has numerous streams of small discharge (Kumba water, Kake water, Mbanga water), springs (Cold spring and Mother Spring) and the crater Lake Barombi Mbo (Akoachere et al., 2018) and over 400 hand-dug wells and numerous boreholes. Kumba experiences two seasons: the wet and the dry season and has a hot and humid equatorial climate with annual rainfall 2298-3400mm and annual temperature 27°C (Akoachere and Ngwesse, 2017a). Though Kumba City Council by "Operation Green

City” planted some trees, subsistence farming of food crops in the town is recurrent on the alluvial yellowish red lateritic and sandy soil.

Figure 1: Location Map of Study Area

3 Materials and Methodology

3.1 Materials

A map of Kumba was used during the reconnaissance stage of this work. The Garmin 30 GPS (Global Positioning System) with precision of 3m was used to take coordinates (spatial data) of the various wells and boreholes. A plumb bob attached to a 100m ribbon was used to measure the level of water table and the depth of wells. Parametres were recorded in a field notebook. A sampling container was used to collect sample water for chemical analysis. Microsoft Excel and some GIS tools such as ArcGIS (Version 10.61), Global Mapper, and Golden Surfer (Version 12) were equally used to analyse and display spatial information in the form of maps.

3.2 Methodology

This study involved two main sources of data collection: primary and secondary. Secondary data were obtained from already existing data in the area and from relevant books, journals and internet. Primary data were obtained from the field by visual observation (the position of the well to the nearest contaminants and the type of soils found in the area where the well was dug and also through interviews and then analyses of the results. Summarily, field methodology and office work were used for the completion of this study. In the field, wells were randomly selected, due to the fact that not every well owner granted permission for their wells to be sampled. The map of the

study area was gotten from the Kumba I Council. The apparatus used for the geolocation on the field were a GPS receiver (GPS Dakota 10) a tape of 50 m long a plumb bomb.

In the office, this map was geo-referenced using ArcGIS 10.16 software. The data was captured through heads-up digitizing in Arc Map 10.61. The final layout was prepared using the mapping functions of the same software. The wells locations were captured using GPS. The various spatial features (well location, elevation, the X and Y coordinates) were digitized. For the samples collection, thirty well locations were identified. These locations were identified in such a way that the wells were evenly distributed over the study area. Collection of data from the field (spatial data and descriptive data). Still in the office, establishing connection between spatial data and descriptive data was done; field data were inputted into Excel and later read in ArcGIS. Maps were realized and then interpreted.

The water samples collected from the 30 representative hand dug wells were taken for chemical analysis to the Chemistry Laboratory of the University of Buea-Cameroon. Before collection the bottles were washed and rinsed with distilled water. After collection of the samples, 3 drops of concentrated nitric acid was pipetted into each water samples to prevent oxidants from reacting with the water. The following tests were carried out in the laboratory; pH (using a pH meter), Temperature (using a thermometer), Electrical conductivity (Conductivity meter), Chloride (titration), Sulphate (spectrophotometry) and Nitrate (titration).

Figure 2: Flash with glass for transportation

Figure 3: plastic to collect well water Conservation of bottles

4 Results and interpretation

4.1 Physico-Chemical Parameters of Well Water from Different Points in Anglican Quarter

Table 1: Laboratory results for chemical parameters of wells (Department of Chemistry University of Buea)

Sample	pH	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Nitrate (NO_3) in mg/L	AgNO_3 in MI	Chloride mg/L	Sulphate mg/L
W1	6.53	224	51.10	1.0	35.50	8.75
W2	6.38	326	45.24	1.1	39.05	0.25
W3	6.38	280	50.43	0.8	28.40	0.125
W4	6.34	335	30.12	0.9	31.95	1.00
W5	6.34	375	30.32	1.1	39.05	1.75
W6	6.33	439	40.44	1.2	42.60	0.125
W7	6.38	286	41.38	0.9	31.95	1.80
W8	6.39	166	52.15	0.5	17.75	6.60
W9	6.36	204	45.15	0.5	17.75	3.00
W10	6.35	327	50.10	0.8	28.40	0.125
W11	6.37	279	49.15	0.8	28.40	9.75
W12	6.35	287	45.12	1.1	39.05	4.00
W13	6.35	254	43.12	0.6	21.30	1.00
W14	6.34	323	35.17	0.8	28.40	0.50
W15	6.35	358	35.28	1.0	35.50	1.25
W16	6.33	321	35.32	0.7	24.85	1.50
W17	6.34	291	37.32	0.7	24.85	1.75
W18	6.34	296	39.42	0.9	17.75	2.15
W19	6.36	184	40.15	0.6	21.30	7.65
W20	6.36	173	40.14	0.9	31.95	4.50
W21	6.43	192	41.15	0.5	17.75	2.75
W22	6.45	162	41.13	0.7	24.85	9.00

W23	6.33	281	42.15	1.0	35.50	3.75
W24	6.31	245	35.16	0.7	24.85	1.00
W25	6.32	263	35.18	0.6	21.30	0.75
W26	6.31	324	50.12	0.8	28.45	0.125
W27	6.31	320	40.13	0.7	24.85	2.00
W28	6.33	342	41.14	0.9	31.95	2.75
W29	6.35	348	43.15	1.0	35.50	9.75
W30	6.34	198	30.45	0.5	17.75	1.80

Figure 4: Map of Chemical Parameters of wells

- **p^H:** The p^H of the sampled wells vary from 6.31- 6.53 but the norms of WHO and the EU should range from 6.5 to 9.5. From the bar chart below, it is clear that only W1 met the norms of WHO. This means the other wells did not meet the norms of WHO and so are slightly acidic depending on their concentrations. The acidity of the well can be harmful to the skin especially for those who bath with the well water.

Figure 5: Data Analysis for pH level

Figure 5 shows that the chloride levels ranged between 17.75mg/L and 42.6mg/L with W6 having the highest value for chloride. The WHO norms for chloride is 250mg/l and no well sample went above limit. In this case the chloride level should be added to the wells. This is because chloride is one of the aspects used for the disinfection of water but needs to be measured depending on the quantity of water.

Figure 6: Data Analysis for Chloride

The level of Sulfate in the well was too low which is an indication that the Sulfate levels of the well meets the requirements of WHO whose limit is 250mg/l. None of the samples exceeded these sample level.

Figure 7: Sulphate Levels in wells

Nitrate is one of the most dangerous contaminant found in water. The WHO limit in water is 50mg/L. If exceeded, it is regarded as one of the causes of methemoglobinemia (blue baby syndrome) in infants as well as potential risk of stomach cancer in adults (Rossiter *et al*, 2010). Nitrate is a nitrogenous compound that when in excess in portable water can cause reduction of oxygen capacity of blood, shortness of breath and blueness of the skin. From the analysis, W1, W3, W8, W10 and W26 exceeded the WHO limit, meaning these wells are not good for consumption. The lowest well recording was W4 with concentration of 30mg/l.

Figure 8: Nitrate Levels in wells

Figure 8 shows the norms for electrical conductivity of portable water which according to WHO is 2500 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$. From the analysis, no well reached the WHO limit, meaning the conductivity levels was ok. Electrical conductivity is also associated with total dissolved solids. Conductivity is a numeric measure of the capacity of an aqueous solution to pass an electric current. Pure water has a conductivity of 1 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ and it is not expected to conduct electricity.

Figure 9: Electrical Conductivity Levels in wells

4.2 Wells and their various contaminants

The contaminants and the various aspects of the wells are shown in the following maps:

Figure 10: Locations of the wells and their contaminant source (Pit toilet, Sewage tank, and Dustbin)

Figure 11: Distances from wells to the sources of contaminants $10m \leq 15m$

We realise that 50% of the wells fall in this range. The standard distance between a well to a contaminant source should be at least 15m, so wells above this range are not likely to be contaminated.

Figure 12: Distances from wells to the sources of contaminants 0m ≤5m

Three wells in this range are to be discussed that is W1, W26 and W28 indicated in red coloured squares. W1 recorded high levels in nitrate of 51.10mg/L and a p^H of 6.53, W26 had high levels in nitrate of 50.12mg/L but has a high p^H of 6.36 which is slightly acidic and W28 has a p^H of 6.33 and recorded a nitrate level of 41.14mg/L.

Figure 13: Displaying various levels of the electrical conductivity level in different colour.

Figure 14: p^h Map of the various wells.

From figure 14, it can be noted that only W1 met up with the norms, implying that the rest of the wells (W2 -W30) did not meet the prescriptions, thus, 96% of wells studied are slightly acidic.

5 Conclusion

From the above analyses, it can be concluded that the chloride and sulfate levels of the wells had no major problems. The main contaminants discovered were at the level of nitrate and the p^h which exceeded the WHO limits. The nitrate levels of wells had an average value of 40mg/l but W1, W3, W8, W10 and W26 had values above 50mg/l, which is in line with WHO. The proximity of the well to possible contaminant too was a major concern as the standard distance from a well to a possible contaminant is 15m, 50% of the wells had possible contaminants less than 15m away and the others above 15m. Localizing the wells and the proximity to possible contaminants source using GIS as a tool, has proven that wells with shallow water tables and lesser proximity to possible contaminants have shown a high degree of contamination like W1, W26 and W28. Just one well (W1) met the standard of WHO for p^h with a value of 6.53. Since the area is greatly characterized by shallow water tables the wells with the highest depth where W24 and W25 respectively. It was also realized that all the wells fall under unconfined aquifer reasons why there is an increase in water levels (surface water infiltration) and easy contamination of well water. It was also concluded that 97.7 % of wells were slightly acidic from W2-W30. It was also found that not all the wells with proximity to their contaminant sources were contaminated. Most of the wells are unconfined aquifer given the fact that the well with highest depth was 8m. The quality of well water used by households has been a major challenge for developing countries including Cameroon in general, and Kumba in particular. For a sustainable well water management, the sensitization of the community is needed by the authorities concerned in order to reduce the rate of contamination by proposing health map plan or ameliorate the supply public system of water (PSW).

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